

Exploring the Personality Profile of Selected Korean Drama (K-Drama) Fans in the Philippines Using the HEXACO Model

Frederick Edward T. Fabella ^{a*}

^a *FEU Roosevelt Graduate School, Cainta, Rizal, Philippines.*

Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analyzed, interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

This is a descriptive correlational study that attempted to investigate the personality profile of Korean Drama (K-drama) fans in the Philippines, which was conducted in October of 2022. The HEXACO Personality Inventory – Revised, 60-item short version was used which consists of 6 domain scales, namely: Honesty-Humility, Emotionality, Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness and Openness to Experience. A researcher-made 15-item K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire was created measuring the respondents' degree of enjoyment of the 15 popular attributes of K-dramas. Through purposive self-selection, 70 K-drama fans volunteered to answer the online version of these 2 questionnaires. Between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their HEXACO scores in Humility-Honesty, Emotionality and Conscientiousness, low positive relationships were found, with the strongest positive relationship observed in Emotionality. While between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and HEXACO scores in Extraversion, Agreeableness and Openness to Experience, low negative relationships were found, with the strongest negative relationship observed in Extraversion.

*Corresponding author: Email: erickfabella@yahoo.com;

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1. INTRODUCTION

TV networks in South Korea began producing dramas in the 1960's. When it became legal to earn revenue from advertisers in the 1970's, more TV dramas were produced. The variety of Korean dramas (K-dramas) increased in the 1980's. Competition between the TV networks intensified in the 1990's as governmental censorship and control relaxed. When the Internet came into being, K-dramas gained a much wider reach in 2000's and their popularity increased among a global audience. Famous international tourist spots had now become the locations in the production of many K-dramas with the goal of attracting a larger worldwide viewership [1].

2002 was the initial year that the export of Korean TV programs experienced a dramatic boom. An increasing demand from the Taiwan, China, Vietnam, Indonesia, Malaysia, and the preference of Korean drama in Japan at that time shows evidence of this [2].

A number of studies have attempted to explore the factors that have led to the popularity of K-dramas in other countries.

US viewers of K-dramas through Netflix was examined in a 2019 study. Those who watched K-dramas were found to exhibit a significant degree of emotional involvement in the romantic stories. By identifying the love themes, the viewers related their personal lives and thoughts to the K-drama narrative. This, in turn produced the experience of pleasure for the US audience [3].

One possible factor for the attraction towards K-dramas are their eye-catching titles. A qualitative study was conducted to analyze the denotative and connotative meanings of K-drama titles. It found that the titles did not fully represent the dramas themselves and were intended as a marketing tool. The titles were crafted to stimulate emotion in the reader [4].

A study was conducted to investigate the impact of the characteristics of Korean trendy drama on the attitudes of the consumers among others. It found that affection and affinity possessed a positive effect on the consumer attitude towards K-dramas [5].

In a study anchored on the Disposition Theory, it attempted to investigate whether strong

dispositions toward characters were necessary in order for American viewers to enjoy watching K-dramas. It found that such dispositions were necessary to elicit the emotional responses that are essential in the success of such K-dramas [6].

Due to the growing popularity of K-dramas, one study was able to establish that students in Indonesia were developing an addiction to these shows that could possibly have detrimental effects to their quality of sleep [7].

Among Korean viewers of K-dramas, a study found that there is a growing expectation that such shows should mirror more realistically the actual issues that Korean society is facing, as more and more K-dramas were veering towards fantasy themes. It also asserts that K-dramas serve a function of representing social problems and initiating dialog about them [8].

One factor that has perhaps increased tourism in South Korea are the K-dramas that feature attractive sceneries and locations. A study utilizing a focus group approach on Singaporean female tourists who were regular viewers of K-dramas found that these shows in part motivated them to visit these locations. It further found that those who visited Korea were more inclined to begin viewing K-dramas [9].

In yet another study involving Malaysian tourists in South Korea, K-dramas have been established as a factor that drives tourism from this country. In addition, it found that K-dramas influenced the Malaysian tourists' view of South Korea as a place for relaxation, cultural exploration, family and social bonding [10].

Not only has K-dramas driven increased tourism in South Korea, but it has also been found to influence fashion and conduct in other countries. A study among Indonesian peer groups investigated the growing impact of K-dramas on their dress and behavior [11].

And in an international survey across 18 countries done in 2021, over 49 percent of the respondents claimed that K-dramas were quite popular in their countries [12].

Despite all these studies that demonstrate the ever-growing popularity of K-dramas, the question of what kind of people or personality

types are prone to becoming K-drama fans has not clearly been answered. It is for this reason that this study was conducted.

In order to discover the personality profile of K-drama fans among a selected number of Philippine respondents, the HEXACO Personality Inventory – Revised was utilized. The 60-item short version was used which consists of 6 domain scales, namely: Honesty-Humility, Emotionality, Extraversion, Agreeableness (versus Anger), Conscientiousness and Openness to Experience. Each domain was measured by 10 items using a 5-point Likert scale [13].

A number of past researches have demonstrated HEXACO's predictive advantages over the Big Five Factor model of personality [14], which is the primary reason why the former was chosen for this study.

A researcher-made K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire composed of 15 items was created to measure the respondents' enjoyment of these shows. These items were based on "15 Reasons Why K-dramas Are Extremely Addictive." [15] The researcher-made questionnaire similarly used a 5-point Likert scale for uniformity.

This study specifically sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores?
2. What are the HEXACO scores of the respondents among the following 6 domain scales
 - 2.1 Honesty-Humility;
 - 2.2 Emotionality;
 - 2.3 Extraversion;
 - 2.4 Agreeableness;
 - 2.5 Conscientiousness;
 - 2.6 Openness to Experience?
3. Is there a relationship between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their 6 HEXACO domain scale scores?

2. METHODOLOGY

The HEXACO Personality Inventory – Revised 60-item short version was utilized. A Google Forms online survey combining the HEXACO

and the researcher-made K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire was created.

Volunteer respondents who are K-drama fans were invited through social media. 70 volunteers from Marikina and Quezon City in Metro Manila and San Mateo and Rodriguez in Rizal agreed to answer the online survey. Their informed consent was obtained but their identities were kept anonymous. The respondents consisted of 6 males and 64 females and had a mean age of 21.09.

This study is limited by the availability of volunteer-respondents who are actual K-drama fans. A further limitation is that the K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire is a researcher-made instrument, which underwent content validation.

3. RESULTS

The following tables show the data obtained and the statistical treatments necessary to address the research questions.

4. DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the 15 researcher-made items of the K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire and the weighted mean of the responses of the 70 respondents per item. Among these 15 attributes of K-dramas, the item with the highest enjoyment rank is "unique and unexpected story or plot" (item 3) while the lowest is "easy to marathon watch" (item 6).

Table 2 shows the respondents' scores in the 6 domain scales of the HEXACO 60-item version. The respondents appear to have the highest scores in Emotionality, followed by Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Honesty-Humility, Agreeableness and Extraversion in that order.

Table 3 presents the relationship between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Humility-Honesty scores. Based on a Pearson – r computation, an r value of 0.074 was obtained, which indicates a low positive correlation between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Humility-Honesty scores.

Table 4 shows the relationship between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Emotionality scores. Based on a Pearson – r computation, an r value of 0.2422 was obtained,

which indicates a low positive correlation between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Emotionality scores.

Table 5 presents the relationship between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Extraversion scores. Based on a Pearson – r computation, an r value of -0.1439 was obtained, which indicates a low negative correlation between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Extraversion scores.

Table 6 shows the relationship between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Agreeableness scores. Based on a Pearson – r computation, an r value of -0.0524 was obtained, which indicates a low negative correlation between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Agreeableness scores.

Table 7 presents the relationship between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Conscientiousness scores. Based on a Pearson – r computation, an r value of 0.0856 was

obtained, which indicates a low positive correlation between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Conscientiousness scores.

Table 8 presents the relationship between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Openness to Experience scores. Based on a Pearson – r computation, an r value of -0.0314 was obtained, which indicates a low negative correlation between the respondents' K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and their Openness to Experience scores.

Table 9 summarizes the preceding 6 Pearson r computations presenting the r values obtained and the relationships observed. Between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and Humility-Honesty, Emotionality and Conscientiousness, low positive relationships were found, with the strongest positive relationship observed in Emotionality. Between K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores and Extraversion, Agreeableness and Openness to Experience, low negative relationships were found, with the strongest negative relationship observed in Extraversion.

Table 1. K-drama enjoyment questionnaire results

Item	Statement	Weighted Mean (70 respondents)	Rank
1	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the beautiful actresses or handsome actors.	4.386	10
2	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the fashionable outfits of the cast.	4.357	12
3	I enjoy K-Dramas because of their unique and unexpected story or plot.	4.9	1
4	I enjoy K-Dramas because of their delightful and exciting story or plot.	4.857	2
5	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the charming sense of humor and antics.	4.843	3
6	I enjoy K-Dramas because they are easy to marathon watch.	4.186	15
7	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the mind-enriching viewing experience.	4.586	7
8	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the delicious Korean food-eating scenes.	4.257	13
9	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the cinematography.	4.7	5
10	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the locations.	4.657	6
11	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the soundtrack.	4.371	11
12	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the script.	4.457	9
13	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the romantic moments and tasteful kissing scenes.	4.128	14
14	I enjoy K-Dramas because of the family-friendly themes.	4.714	4
15	I enjoy K-Dramas because there are always new couple pairings of love teams.	4.5	8

Table 2. HEXACO domain scale scores

Domain Scale	Weighted Mean (70 respondents)	Standard Deviation
Honesty-Humility	34.557	5.188
Emotionality	36.271	4.390
Extraversion	28.657	4.177
Agreeableness	32.071	5.536
Conscientiousness	34.614	4.891
Openness to Experience	35.629	5.336

Table 3. Relationship between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and humility-honesty

Pearson – r computation	
X Values	X and Y Combined
$\Sigma = 4753$	N = 70
Mean = 67.9	$\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = 115.9$
$\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1320.3$	
	R Calculation
Y Values	$r = \frac{\Sigma((X - My)(Y - Mx))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$
$\Sigma = 2419$	$r = 115.9 / \sqrt{((1320.3)(1857.271))} = 0.074$
Mean = 34.557	
$\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 1857.271$	
	Meta Numerics (cross-check)
	r = 0.074

The r = 0.074, which indicates a low positive correlation

Table 4. Relationship between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and emotionality

Pearson – r computation	
X Values	X and Y Combined
$\Sigma = 4753$	N = 70
Mean = 67.9	$\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = 320.9$
$\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1320.3$	
	R Calculation
Y Values	$r = \frac{\Sigma((X - My)(Y - Mx))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$
$\Sigma = 2539$	$r = 320.9 / \sqrt{((1320.3)(1329.843))} = 0.2422$
Mean = 36.271	
$\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 1329.843$	
	Meta Numerics (cross-check)
	r = 0.2422

The r = 0.242, which indicates a low positive correlation

Table 5. Relationship between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and extraversion

Pearson – r computation	
X Values	X and Y Combined
$\Sigma = 4753$	N = 70
Mean = 67.9	$\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = -181.4$
$\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1320.3$	
	R Calculation
Y Values	$r = \frac{\Sigma((X - My)(Y - Mx))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$
$\Sigma = 2006$	$r = -181.4 / \sqrt{((1320.3)(1203.771))} = -0.1439$
Mean = 28.657	
$\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 1203.771$	
	Meta Numerics (cross-check)
	r = -0.1439

The r = -0.144, which indicates a low negative correlation

Table 6. Relationship between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and agreeableness

Pearson – r computation	
X Values $\Sigma = 4753$ Mean = 67.9 $\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1320.3$	X and Y Combined N = 70 $\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = -87.5$
Y Values $\Sigma = 2245$ Mean = 32.071 $\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 2114.643$	R Calculation $r = \frac{\Sigma((X - Mx)(Y - My))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$ $r = -87.5 / \sqrt{((1320.3)(2114.643))} = -0.0524$
	Meta Numerics (cross-check) r = -0.0524

The r = -0.052, which indicates a low negative correlation

Table 7. Relationship between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and conscientiousness

Pearson – r computation	
X Values $\Sigma = 4753$ Mean = 67.9 $\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1320.3$	X and Y Combined N = 70 $\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = 126.3$
Y Values $\Sigma = 2423$ Mean = 34.614 $\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 1650.586$	R Calculation $r = \frac{\Sigma((X - Mx)(Y - My))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$ $r = 126.3 / \sqrt{((1320.3)(1650.586))} = 0.0856$
	Meta Numerics (cross-check) r = 0.0856

The r = 0.086, which indicates a low positive correlation

Table 8. Relationship between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and openness to experience

Pearson – r computation	
X Values $\Sigma = 4753$ Mean = 67.9 $\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 1320.3$	X and Y Combined N = 70 $\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = -50.6$
Y Values $\Sigma = 2494$ Mean = 35.629 $\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 1964.343$	R Calculation $r = \frac{\Sigma((X - Mx)(Y - My))}{\sqrt{((SSx)(SSy))}}$ $r = -50.6 / \sqrt{((1320.3)(1964.343))} = -0.0314$
	Meta Numerics (cross-check) r = -0.0314

The r = -0.031, which indicates a low negative correlation

Table 9. Summary of relationships between K-drama enjoyment questionnaire scores and HEXACO domain scales

Domain Scale	Pearson r value	Relationship
Honesty-Humility	0.074	low positive correlation
Emotionality	0.242	low positive correlation
Extraversion	-0.144	low negative correlation
Agreeableness	-0.052	low negative correlation
Conscientiousness	0.086	low positive correlation
Openness to Experience	-0.031	low negative correlation

5. CONCLUSIONS

For this set of respondents who are fans of K-dramas in the Philippines, it is interesting to note that their HEXACO scores show that their highest domain scale is Emotionality and their lowest domain scale is Extraversion. In addition, the strongest positive relationship found with K-drama Enjoyment Questionnaire scores was in Emotionality and the strongest negative relationship was found in Extraversion.

Based on these results, the HEXACO personality profile of these selected Philippine fans of K-drama, would tend to possess very slightly higher Emotionality, Conscientiousness and Honesty-Humility scores and very slightly lower Extraversion, Agreeableness and Openness to Experience scores. Further study is recommended on a larger group of K-drama fans of varying age groups and from different social sectors to confirm these initial findings on the HEXACO personality profile of Philippine K-drama fans.

CONSENT

As per international standard or university standard, Participants' written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Kalbi. K-drama series – A brief history of K-dramas. Korean Culture Blog; 2016. Available:https://koreancultureblog.com/2016/10/10/k-drama-series-a-brief-history-of-k-dramas/ Access on October 22, 2022.
2. Lee MH. Study on characteristics of Korean drama exports to 8 Asian countries. The Journal of the Korea Contents Association. 2007;7(9):34–43.

3. Available:https://doi.org/10.5392/jkca.2007.7.9.034
3. Ju H. Korean TV drama viewership on netflix: Transcultural Affection, romance, and identities. Journal of International and Intercultural Communication. 2019;13(1):32–48. Available:https://doi.org/10.1080/17513057.2019.1606269
4. Pakpahan F. Denotation and connotation in Korean drama titles of 2019-2020. KnE Social Sciences. 2021:318–327. Available:https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v5i4.8691
5. Chae H, Park JH, Ko E. The effect of attributes of Korean trendy drama on consumer attitude, national image, and consumer acceptance intention for sustainable Hallyu culture. Journal of Global Fashion Marketing. 2019;11(1):18–36. Available:https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2019.1680305
6. Chuang LM, Lee HE. Korean wave: Enjoyment factors of Korean dramas in the U.S. International Journal of Intercultural Relations, 2013;37(5):594–604. Available:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2013.07.003
7. Malfasari E, Febtrina R, Herniyanti R, Utari EM. Korean drama addiction and the quality of sleep of Indonesian students. Indonesian Journal of Global Health Research. 2019;1(1):59–72. Available:https://doi.org/10.37287/ijghr.v1i1.8
8. Baldacchino JP, Park EJ. Between fantasy and realism. Brill; 2020. Available:https://brill.com/view/journals/ejea/20/2/article-p285_3.xml Access on October 22, 2022.
9. Chan B. Film-induced tourism in Asia: A case study of Korean television drama and female viewers' motivation to visit Korea. Tourism Culture & Communication. 2007;7(3):207–224. Available:https://doi.org/10.3727/109830407782212510
10. Teh PY, Goh HC. Does Korean drama have a real influence? An analysis of Malaysia outbound tourists to South Korea. Tourism Culture & Communication. 2016;16(3):147–160. Available:https://doi.org/10.3727/109830416x14750895902882

11. Kusumasari D. Intensity of Korean drama program in television, peer group interactions, and its influence toward K-style imitation behavior among teenagers. *Jurnal Komunikasi Ikatan Sarjana Komunikasi Indonesia*. 2017;2(1):48. Available:<https://doi.org/10.25008/jkiski.v2i1.92>
12. Statista Research Department. Korean drama (K-drama) popularity worldwide 2021. Statista; 2022. Available:<https://www.statista.com/statistics/999239/south-korea-korean-drama-popularity-worldwide/> Access on October 22, 2022.
13. Ashton MC, Lee K. The HEXACO-60: A short measure of the major dimensions of personality. *Journal of Personality Assessment*. 2009;91:340-345.
14. Aghababaei N, Arji A. Well-being and the HEXACO model of personality. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 2014;56:139–142. Available:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2013.08.037>
15. Corp., A. B. S.-C. B. N. (n.d.). 15 reasons why K-dramas are extremely addictive. Metro. Style. Available:<https://metro.style/culture/spotlight/15-reasons-why-kdramas-are-addictive/8691> Access on October 22, 2022.

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